

SPASE 3.0 Dataset Functional Requirements

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Accepted Use Cases/Priorities (see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17553643>):

- **High:** $\geq 80\%$ or fundamental functionality.
Use cases 1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 18, 19, 23, 24, 25, 26, 30, 31, 32, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 49, 50, 51, 53, 54, 55, 59, 60, 61, 65, 66.
- **Medium:** $\geq 66.67\%$ or useful/desired functionality.
Use cases 4, 17, 20, 21, 22, 29, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 52, 56, 57, 58, 62.
- **Low:** supplementary functionality.
Use cases 3, 27, 28, 33, 46, 47, 48, 63, 64.

Use Case Notes:

- Cases 27 and 28 request support for storing related publication information in SPASE 3.0. The interoperability requirement of SPASE 3.0 results in these relation types being supported, but it is not prioritized. Similar, at least partially, case 3.
- Cases 4 and 45 support creating SPASE records from external generalist repositories (e.g., Zenodo) with the caveat that this should not prevent SPASE 3.0 from requiring fields that those repositories do not or the reverse (e.g., the description field or the publisher). One important item in use case 4 is considered a critical high-level requirement, specifically being able to create correct SPASE records in 5-10 minutes (see also use case 10).
- Cases 46, 47, 48 (see notes; integration with an online OSDMP tool is an implementation/service idea, not to determine what fields go into SPASE 3.0; also, related to research data).
- Cases 9, 10 (do not provide requirements for specific fields, but regarded as a critical service).

- A separate study will be needed to extract items needed on SPASE landing pages. Similarly for instrument landing pages, missions/observatories, and similar items indicated in the use cases.

Ref.	Reference Description		Comments
*	Globally unique PID metadata shall allow for: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifier scheme name (e.g., DOI) 2. Identifier scheme version 3. Identifier scheme URI (e.g., https://doi.org/) 4. Identifier code in the scheme (e.g., 10.5281... or item/term code) 5. Identifier URI (e.g., https://doi.org/10.5281...) 		Either identifier URI or combination of identifier scheme URI and identifier code in the scheme is required. Globally unique PID metadata is also used for terms from controlled vocabularies. The term name is supported elsewhere.
**	Person metadata shall allow for: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Given name or initial 2. Family name 3. Name 4. Contact email 5. Globally unique PID metadata* (e.g., ORCID metadata) 		Both given and family names are required, except for single name persons, where name is required. Given name includes first and middle names or initials. Contact email is required for contact roles.
**	Organization metadata shall allow for: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Name 2. Contact email 3. Globally unique PID metadata* (e.g., ROR metadata) 		Contact email is required for organizations (including teams) in contact roles.
***	Units metadata shall allow for: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Preferred units string 2. Units string compliant with syntax defined by units scheme 3. Units scheme name (e.g., VOUnits) 4. Units scheme version 		

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Units scheme URI 6. Units globally unique PID metadata* (e.g., QUDT metadata) 		
****	<p>Coordinate system metadata shall allow for:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Coordinate system name 2. Coordinate system globally unique PID metadata* 3. Coordinate representation 4. Coordinate representation globally unique PID metadata* 		
*****	<p>Extension metadata shall allow for:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Property name 2. Property globally unique PID metadata* 3. Value 4. Value globally unique PID metadata* 	64	
Req. #	Requirement Description	Use Case # / Priority	Comments
1.1	SPASE model shall contain support for metadata for Solar and Space Physics (in-situ, space, and ground based) datasets.	All? (13, 23, 24)	
1.2	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dataset globally unique PID metadata* 2. Dataset name 3. Dataset version 4. Dataset version description 5. Dataset version time ranges 	1, 2, 5, 6, 8, 11, 12, 13, 15, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26,	<p>Metadata release date and Metadata revision date will be auto-generated for new records (required in SPASE 2.X).</p> <p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ResourceID

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Dataset description 7. Metadata release date 8. Metadata revision date 9. Dataset landing page URL 10. Acknowledgement 11. Dataset processing level (e.g., Raw, Uncalibrated, Calibrated, ValueAdded) 12. Link to access or request access to the data 13. Dataset extension metadata***** 	<p>29, 31, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 39, 41, 42, 43, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 64 (all?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ResourceHeader/PriorID • ResourceHeader/DOI • ResourceHeader/ResourceName • ProviderVersion • ResourceHeader/Description • ResourceHeader/ReleaseDate • ResourceHeader/RevisionHistory/RevisionEvent/ReleaseDate • ResourceHeader/PublicationInfo/LandingPageURL • ResourceHeader/Acknowledgement • ProcessingLevel • AccessInformation • Extension
1.3	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for dataset Type metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dataset type name (e.g., Numerical Data, Display Data, Catalog) 2. Dataset type globally unique PID metadata* 	<p>6, 11, 13, 20, 21, 23, 24</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ResourceType • spase:NumericalData • spase:NumericalOutput • spase:DisplayData • spase:DisplayOutput • spase:Catalog
1.4	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for dataset Creator metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creator type (person or organization) 2. Creator (person or organization) metadata** 3. Creator affiliation organization metadata** 4. Creator other role metadata: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4.1. Role name (including creators that also serve as contacts) 4.2. Role globally unique PID metadata* 	<p>5, 7, 11, 14, 17, 31, 34, 35</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ResourceHeader/PublicationInfo/Authors • ResourceHeader/Contact/PersonID • ResourceHeader/Contact/Role • spase:Person/PersonName • spase:Person/ORCIDentifier • spase:Person/Email • spase:Person/OrganizationName • spase:Person/RORIdentifier

1.5	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for dataset Contributor metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Contributor type (person or organization) 2. Contributor (person or organization) metadata** 3. Contributor affiliation organization metadata** 4. Contributor role metadata: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4.1. Role name (including contact roles) 4.2. Role globally unique PID metadata* 	14, 17, 31	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ResourceHeader/Contact/PersonID ● ResourceHeader/Contact/Role ● spase:Person/PersonName ● spase:Person/ORCIDentifier ● spase:Person/Email ● spase:Person/OrganizationName ● spase:Person/RORIdentifier ● ProviderName
1.6	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Publication metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Publisher type (person or organization) 2. Publisher (person or organization) metadata** 3. Publication date <p>Publication date shall be in ISO 8601 format.</p>	5, 11	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ResourceHeader/PublicationInfo/ PublishedBy ● ResourceHeader/PublicationInfo/ PublicationDate
1.7	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Funding metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Funder organization metadata** 2. Award title 3. Award globally unique PID metadata* 	29	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ResourceHeader/Funding/Agency ● ResourceHeader/Funding/Project ● ResourceHeader/Funding/AwardNumber
1.8	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for dataset Metadata License metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Metadata license name 2. Metadata license globally unique PID metadata* 	11, 30, 35	
1.9	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Related Resource metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resource name 2. Resource version 3. Resource description 4. Resource globally unique PID metadata* 	3, 8, 13, 15, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 27, 28, 29, 30,	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ResourceHeader/InformationURL/Name ● ResourceHeader/InformationURL/URL ● ResourceHeader/InformationURL/Description

	<p>5. Relation type name (including CiteWith or similar)</p> <p>6. Relation type globally unique PID metadata*</p> <p>7. Resource type name</p> <p>8. Resource type globally unique PID metadata* (e.g., from DataCite's list)</p> <p>Supported Related Resources (resources required for complete understanding of the dataset, determined by dataset creators) shall include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Reference publications Web pages Documentation with versions Software via provenance relationships with versions Related datasets via provenance relationships with versions (including dataset previous version and new version) 	<p>32, 34, 35, 60, 61, 62</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ResourceHeader/Association/ID ResourceHeader/Association/Association Type InputResourceID
1.10	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Instrument metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Instrument name Instrument globally unique PID metadata* 	<p>1, 6, 7, 12, 20, 35, 39, 48, 49,</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> spase:Instrument/ResourceHeader/ResourceName spase:Instrument/ResourceHeader/DOI InstrumentID
1.11	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Mission/Observatory metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Mission/observatory name Mission/observatory globally unique PID metadata* 	<p>1, 6, 7, 12, 20, 21, 26, 33, 34, 39, 47, 49</p>	<p>Only for datasets associated with the whole Mission/Observatory and not individual instruments?</p>
1.12	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Measurement Type metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Measurement type name Measurement type globally unique PID metadata* 	<p>2, 13, 16, 20, 21, 23, 25, 26, 27, 28, 33, 35, 39</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MeasurementType

1.13	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Observed Region/Subregion (the more specific option being preferred) metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Observed region/subregion name Region/subregion globally unique PID metadata* 	<p>6, 13, 22, 23, 25, 26, 27, 28, 33, 35, 39, 50</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ObservedRegion
1.14	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Phenomenon Type metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Phenomenon type name Phenomenon type globally unique PID metadata* 	<p>2, 20, 21, 24, 33, 35</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PhenomenonType
1.15	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Keyword metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Keyword name Keyword globally unique PID metadata* 	<p>20, 33, 35</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keyword
1.16	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for spectral Wavelength Range metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Minimum wavelength Maximum wavelength Units metadata*** Range name Range globally unique PID metadata* <p>Either minimum and maximum wavelength and units metadata or range name and range globally unique PID metadata shall be included.</p>	<p>13, 33</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SpectralRange <p>Should it be under parameter only?</p>
1.17	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Cadence and Measurement Interval metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Cadence Measurement interval (exposure) <p>Cadence and measurement interval (including minimum and maximum) shall be in ISO 8601 duration format.</p>	<p>13, 63</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> TemporalDescription/Cadence TemporalDescription/Exposure

1.18	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for data Temporal Coverage metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Absolute start time 2. Absolute stop time 3. Relative stop time <p>Absolute start/stop times shall be in ISO 8601 duration format. Relative stop time (estimated stop time relative to real time, i.e. availability delay) shall be in ISO 8601 duration format. Either absolute or relative stop time, but not both, shall be included.</p>	<p>1, 2, 7, 13, 16, 21, 22, 23, 35, 39</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TemporalDescription/TimeSpan/StartDate • TemporalDescription/TimeSpan/StopDate • TemporalDescription/TimeSpan/RelativeStopDate
1.19	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for data Spatial Coverage metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Coordinate system metadata**** 2. Spatial coverage component metadata: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1. Component metadata: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1.1. Component name 2.1.2. Component globally unique PID metadata* 2.2. Center value 2.3. Minimum value 2.4. Maximum value 2.5. Units metadata*** 	<p>58</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SpatialCoverage/CoordinateSystem/CoordinateSystemName • SpatialCoverage/CoordinateSystem/CoordinateRepresentation • SpatialCoverage/CenterLatitude • SpatialCoverage/NorthernmostLatitude • SpatialCoverage/SouthernmostLatitude • SpatialCoverage/CenterLongitude • SpatialCoverage/EasternmostLongitude • SpatialCoverage/WesternmostLongitude • SpatialCoverage/CenterElevation • SpatialCoverage/MinimumElevation • SpatialCoverage/MaximumElevation • SpatialCoverage/Acknowledgement • SpatialCoverage/Description
1.20	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Data Repository metadata:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data repository organization metadata** 	<p>19, 35, 39, 42, 43, 60</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • spase:Repository/ResourceID

	<p>2. Access Rights</p> <p>3. Dataset License metadata:</p> <p>3.1. Dataset license name</p> <p>3.2. Dataset license globally unique PID metadata*</p> <p>4. Dataset Size metadata:</p> <p>4.1. Size</p> <p>4.2. Units metadata***</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● spase:Repository/ResourceHeader/ResourceName ● spase:Repository/ResourceHeader/DOI ● spase:Repository/RORIdentifier ● spase:Repository/re3data ● AccessInformation/AccessRights ● AccessInformation/rightsList ● AccessInformation/DataExtent
1.21	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall, for each data repository, allow for Access Method or Protocol Type metadata:</p> <p>1. Access method/protocol type name</p> <p>2. Access method/protocol type globally unique PID metadata*</p> <p>3. Access method/protocol type documentation URL</p>		<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AccessInformation/AccessURL/Style
1.22	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall, for each access method/protocol type, allow for Data Access metadata:</p> <p>1. Description</p> <p>2. Dataset key</p> <p>3. Data access URL</p> <p>4. Metadata needed to form access protocol call</p> <p>5. File format metadata:</p> <p>5.1. File format name</p> <p>5.2. File format globally unique PID metadata*</p>	<p>13, 15, 16, 17, 30, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 41</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AccessInformation/AccessURL/Description ● AccessInformation/AccessURL/ProductKey ● AccessInformation/AccessURL/URL ● AccessInformation/Format
1.23	<p>Dataset SPASE metadata shall allow for Parameter metadata:</p> <p>1. Parameter name</p> <p>2. Parameter key</p> <p>3. Description</p> <p>4. Object of interest metadata:</p> <p>4.1. Object of interest name</p> <p>4.2. Object of interest globally unique PID metadata*</p>	<p>17, 20, 21, 35, 59, 64, 65, 66</p>	<p>Maps SPASE2.X properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Parameter/Name ● Parameter/ParameterKey ● Parameter/Description ● Parameter/UCD ● Parameter/Field ● Parameter/Particle

	<p>5. Quantity kind metadata: 5.1. Quantity kind name 5.2. Quantity kind globally unique PID metadata*</p> <p>6. Qualifier metadata: 6.1. Qualifier name 6.2. Qualifier globally unique PID metadata*</p> <p>7. Units metadata***</p> <p>8. Dimensionality (dimension sizes)</p> <p>9. Coordinate system metadata****</p> <p>10. Array element metadata: 10.1. Element index 10.2. Element name 10.3. Coordinate system component metadata: 10.3.1. Component name 10.3.2. Component globally unique PID metadata*</p> <p>10.4. Element Units metadata***</p> <p>10.5. Element extension metadata*****</p> <p>11. Parameter extension metadata*****</p> <p>12. Limiting range metadata: 12.1. Quantity kind name 12.2. Quantity kind globally unique PID metadata* 12.3. Range name 12.4. Range globally unique PID metadata* 12.5. Minimum value 12.6. Maximum value 12.7. Units metadata***</p> <p>Cadence, minimum and maximum cadences shall be in ISO 8601 duration format.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Parameter/Mixed ● Parameter/Support ● Parameter/ParticleType ● Parameter/WaveType ● Parameter/ParticleQuantity ● Parameter/WaveQuantity ● Parameter/MixedQuantity ● Parameter/SupportQuantity ● Parameter/Qualifier ● Parameter/Units ● Parameter/Structure/Size ● Parameter/Structure/Element/Units ● Parameter/CoordinateSystem/Coordinate SystemName ● Parameter/CoordinateSystem/Coordinate Representation ● Parameter/RenderingHints (using Parameter extension metadata) ● Parameter/Structure/Element/Name ● Parameter/Structure/Element/Index ● Parameter/Structure/Element/Units ● Parameter/FrequencyRange ● Parameter/WavelengthRange ● Parameter/EnergyRange ● Parameter/MassRange ● Parameter/AzimuthalAngleRange ● Parameter/PolarAngleRange ● Parameter/PitchAngleRange
1.24	Catalog SPASE metadata shall allow for links to external websites separate from provenance and access.	20	

2.1	<p>SPASE metadata shall be reasonably interoperable with other related data models</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. DCAT3, 2. Schema.org, 3. DataCite, 4. FITS/SolarNET, 5. VSO 2.0. 6. ISTEP, 7. HAPI <p>Fields determined to support FAIR in generic search interfaces or interlinking shall be mappable to generic data models, subject to the fields available in those data models.</p> <p>Fields determined to increase usability and understandability, specifically including the dataset PID, shall be mappable to more specific data models (e.g., VSO, ISTEP), subject to the fields available in those data models.</p>	<p>8, 11, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18, 30, 31, 32, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 46</p>	
2.2	<p>SPASE model shall use controlled vocabularies with globally unique PIDs for both vocabularies and vocabulary terms.</p>	<p>29, 33,</p>	
2.3	<p>SPASE model shall include support for identifiers for a maximized number of item types, including region names, measurement types, instruments, missions/observatories, datasets, people, organizations, phenomena, funders, publishers, awards, contributor roles (for data).</p>	<p>29, 33, 34</p>	
2.4	<p>SPASE model shall include support for qualified references for all items, including region names, measurement types, instruments, datasets, people, organizations, phenomena, funders, publishers, awards, contributor roles</p>	<p>29</p>	

(for <u>data</u>), other datasets, other software, other publications, documentation, other artifacts deemed useful to the mission, and so on.		
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